

A Faculty Development Plan on Assessment Literacy of Tertiary Instructors in Davao City

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Abstract

This study investigates the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors in Davao City to guide a faculty development plan. Using a non-experimental quantitative research design, 304 instructors were randomly sampled. An adapted survey questionnaire and statistical methods such as frequency, mean, and ANOVA were employed to assess differences in assessment literacy based on years of service and academic background. Results reveal that the majority of instructors in Davao City possess education degrees, indicating a wide range of teaching experience. Tertiary instructors exhibit strong skills in assessment design, but there is less proficiency observed in analyzing assessment data, particularly among instructors without education degrees. Educational institutions could enhance instructional quality by promoting further education and training in assessment literacy, particularly for non-education degree holders. These findings advocate for the development of a targeted faculty development plan aligned with the study's outcomes.

Keywords: *Assessment literacy, faculty development plan, tertiary instructors, Davao City, Philippines.*

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Introduction

Amidst the ever-evolving educational landscape, the pivotal role of assessment in shaping student learning experiences has garnered heightened significance. As higher education institutions navigate the complexities of diverse learners and evolving pedagogies, the imperative of assessment literacy emerges as a critical focal point.

The concept of teacher assessment literacy, encapsulating the requisite knowledge and skills for effective assessment implementation in classrooms, has long held prominence within educational policy and research agendas (Pastore, 2023). Embracing the transformative trends ushered in by the Fourth Industrial Revolution (IR4.0), educational paradigms emphasize project-based learning, data interpretation, and student involvement in curriculum design, signaling a departure from conventional assessment modalities (Salmon, 2019; Aziz Hussin, 2018). Echoing this shift, the Philippine education system underscores the adoption of diverse strategies for holistic student assessment and success (Plata, 2018; Rosaroso & Rosaroso, 2015).

However, studies reveal persistent gaps in assessment literacy, particularly among language teachers and practitioners of reflective assessment, underscoring the need for targeted training and pedagogical support (Nurdiana, 2020; Chan & Lou, 2020). Moreover, empirical evidence underscores the indispensable role of assessment literacy in designing effective science assessments, coupled with the imperative of instructional enhancements to bolster educators' assessment competencies (Pearson et al., 2015). As educational stakeholders navigate these challenges, the call for comprehensive policies and

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programs to enhance assessment practices in higher education resonates profoundly (Sarmiento et al., 2023).

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors as a basis for the faculty development plan for the academic year 2023 – 2024. This research sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents?
2. What is the level of assessment literacy of tertiary instructors?
3. Is there a significant difference in tertiary instructors' assessment literacy level when analyzed by profile?
4. What faculty development plan can be created based on the result?

Methods

This study employed a non-experimental quantitative design utilizing a descriptive-comparative approach. The researcher conducted this study in Davao City, Philippines, for the academic year 2023 – 2024. There were 304 tertiary instructors who are currently teaching in any higher educational institutions in Davao City who were selected using simple random sampling. This study utilized an adapted survey questionnaire on the study of Ahmadi et al. (2022). The researcher used frequency, mean, and independent samples t-tests to determine the significant difference in terms of years of service and academic background.

Results and Discussions

Table 1. The Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Educational Background	Frequency	Percent
Education Graduate	200	65.80
Education Earner	51	16.80
Non Education Graduate nor Earner	53	17.40
Total	304	100.00
Years of Teaching	Frequency	Percent
0 - 3 years	116	38.20
4 - 7 years	86	28.30
8 - 11 years	32	10.50
12 -15 years	19	6.30
15 years above	51	16.80
Total	304	100.00

The table provides an overview of respondents categorized by their educational background and years of teaching experience. The results reveal that a significant majority, 65.80%, are graduates of teacher education programs. Following this group, 17.40% of respondents are non-education graduates or those who have not completed an education degree, and 16.80% are individuals who have earned some education credits but not a full degree. This indicates that the majority of instructors in higher educational institutions in Davao City hold degrees in education. In terms of teaching experience, the data shows that the largest group, representing 38.20% of respondents, has been teaching for 0 to 3 years. This is followed by those with 4 to 7 years of experience at 28.30%. Teachers with over 15 years of experience make up

16.80% of the respondents, those with 8 to 11 years constitute 10.50%, and the smallest group, with 6.30%, are teachers who have been teaching for 12 to 15 years. This distribution suggests a diverse range of teaching experience among the instructors in the region.

Table 2. Level of Assessment Literacy of Tertiary Instructors

Assessment Literacy	Mean	SD	Descriptive Level
Collaboration	4.29	0.75	Very High
Assessment Design	4.48	0.53	Very High
Item design and Data Collection Method	4.14	0.71	High
Data analysis	3.19	0.86	Moderate
Overall	4.03	0.56	High

The table presents the level of assessment literacy among tertiary instructors. The results indicate that the overall assessment literacy of these instructors has a mean score of 4.03 and a standard deviation of 0.56, corresponding to a descriptive level of high. This means that the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors is frequently evident. The domain with the highest mean score is Assessment Design, which has a mean score of 4.48 and a standard deviation of 0.53. This suggests that tertiary instructors are particularly adept at designing assessments, demonstrating strong skills in this area. Conversely, the domain with the lowest mean score is Data Analysis, which has a mean score of 3.19 and a standard deviation of 0.86. This indicates that, while still competent, instructors show less proficiency in analyzing assessment data compared to other areas. Overall, these results highlight both strengths and areas for improvement in the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors.

Furthermore, this finding aligns with Massey et al. (2020), indicating a high level of confidence in various practical assessment methods. However, it contrasts with Akhtar et al. (2021), who found that the assessment literacy of prospective teachers was inadequate, highlighting that teacher educators primarily used summative assessment approaches. Similarly, Atjonen et al. (2022) noted that student teachers find it challenging to discuss assessment topics with their peers. Meanwhile, in the study of Booc (2023), the result shows that the lowest mean score of capabilities of teachers is data analysis which is similar to the result.

Table 3. Significant Difference on Assessment Literacy in Terms of Educational Background

Factors	Educational Background						Decision	Having Differences
	A	B	C	Total	f	Sig		
Collaboration	4.42	4.20	3.92	4.29	10.166	0.000	Significant	A and C
Assessment Design	4.55	4.42	4.25	4.48	7.301	0.001	Significant	A and C
Item design and Data Collection Method	4.18	4.06	4.08	4.14	0.787	0.456	Not Significant	
Data analysis	4.23	4.13	4.01	4.17	1.462	0.233	Not Significant	
Assessment Literacy	4.35	4.20	4.07	4.28	6.079	0.003	Significant	A and C
Legend: A - Education Graduate; B - Education Earner; C - Not Education Graduate nor Earner								

The table presents the significant difference in assessment literacy based on the educational background of respondents. The results show that assessment literacy has a p-value of less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference between groups. Specifically, the mean assessment literacy score for Education Graduates is 4.35, while for Non-Education Graduates or Earners, it is 4.07. This suggests that Education Graduates have higher assessment literacy compared to their counterparts who did not graduate from an education program or have only partially completed such a program. Moreover, the

indicators for Collaboration and Assessment Design also show statistically significant differences, with p-values of 0.000 and 0.01, respectively. Education Graduates have higher mean scores in these areas compared to Non-Education Graduates or Earners. These results indicate that Education Graduates possess higher overall assessment literacy and excel specifically in collaborative practices and assessment design. This further underscores the importance of formal education in teaching, as it appears to equip instructors with superior skills in these critical areas.

This finding implies that having a formal education background in teaching significantly enhances an individual's assessment literacy. Consequently, institutions may benefit from encouraging or requiring further education and training in assessment literacy for instructors who do not have an education degree, aiming to improve overall instructional quality.

The result supports the study by Somosot and Relox (2023), which found that non-education graduates teaching in HEIs had trouble handling diverse students, lacked teaching resources, and struggled with academic requirements. This shows a big difference in assessment skills between education and non-education graduates. Similarly, Balagtas et al. (2010) also found a difference in assessment literacy between these two groups. With this, Newkirk (2024) study's results suggest that while all new teachers benefit from induction programs focusing on lesson planning, instructional strategies, and mentorship, second-career educators particularly need additional support to enhance their assessment literacy. Moreover, to address this concern teacher should also be open to the trends in education (Booc et al., 2024).

Table 4. Significant Difference in Assessment Literacy in Terms of Years of Teaching

Factor	Years of Teaching						Total	f	Sig	Decision
	0 - 3 years	4 - 7 years	8 - 11 years	12 -15 years	15 years above					
Collaboration	4.29	4.24	4.27	4.25	4.43	4.29	0.57	0.69	Not Significant	
Assessment Design	4.48	4.44	4.54	4.55	4.46	4.48	0.30	0.88	Not Significant	
Item design and Data Collection Method	4.19	4.07	4.03	4.11	4.24	4.14	0.77	0.55	Not Significant	
Data analysis	4.27	4.09	4.13	4.13	4.15	4.17	0.60	0.66	Not Significant	
Assessment Literacy	4.31	4.22	4.24	4.26	4.32	4.28	0.39	0.82	Not Significant	

The table shows the significant difference in assessment literacy based on years of teaching experience. The results indicate that the p-value is 0.82, which is greater than 0.05. This means there is no statistically significant difference in assessment literacy among respondents with different years of teaching experience. This suggests that the length of teaching experience does not significantly impact the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors. Regardless of whether instructors have been teaching for a few years or several decades, their assessment literacy levels are similar.

Professional development in assessment literacy should be uniformly targeted across all instructors, irrespective of their years of teaching experience. This approach ensures that all instructors, regardless of their tenure, maintain a high level of assessment literacy, ultimately benefiting student learning outcomes.

The result differs from Massey et al. (2020), which emphasizes the need to tailor assessment training programs for college instructors according to their prior teaching experience. Similarly, Rezai (2023) advocates for incorporating teacher assessment literacy into both pre-service and in-service teacher training courses.

Faculty Development Plan

The tables show the Improvement Goals, SMART Goals, Output, Monitoring System, and Person In-charge. The improvement goals for each group focus on enhancing Data Analysis, Assessment Design, and Collaboration. Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound (SMART) goals are

tailored to each improvement area. The expected outcomes of achieving these SMART goals include improved data interpretation, more effective assessment tools, and enhanced team synergy. Strategies to achieve these goals involve detailed methods and activities such as training workshops, data modeling techniques, and collaborative project planning. A monitoring system utilizing tools and processes will track progress and effectiveness, ensuring that milestones are met. Individuals have been designated as responsible for implementing and overseeing each part of the plan to ensure accountability and success.

Figure 5. A Short Term Faculty Development Plan on Assessment Literacy in Terms of Educational Background

Improvement Goals	SMART Goals	Output	Strategies	Monitoring System	Person In-charge
A. Education Graduates					
Enhance Data Analysis skills	Achieve a 10% increase in Data Analysis skills by year-end.	Improved data interpretation and usage.	Advanced workshops on data analysis tools and techniques.	Pre- and post-assessment surveys, performance reviews.	Department Head, External Experts
Strengthen Assessment Design	Develop innovative assessment tools by mid-year.	New and effective assessment tools.	Collaborative design sessions and peer reviews.	Regular feedback sessions, assessment tool evaluations.	Senior Faculty, Assessment Committee
Foster Collaboration	Increase collaborative projects by 20% within a year.	More collaborative teaching projects.	Team-based projects and regular collaborative meetings.	Project tracking, collaboration effectiveness surveys.	Faculty Development Coordinator
B. Education Earners					
Improve Data Analysis skills	Increase proficiency in data analysis by 15% in six months.	Enhanced analysis reports.	Targeted training on data analysis methodologies.	Skills assessment tests, project-based evaluations.	Training Coordinator, Data Analysis Expert
Advance Assessment Design	Create diverse assessment formats within eight months.	Variety of assessment formats.	Interactive workshops and mentorship programs.	Ongoing project monitoring, design quality checks.	Faculty Mentor, Curriculum Specialist
Enhance Collaboration	Engage in 10% more collaborative activities in a year.	Increased joint projects and initiatives.	Peer collaboration sessions and interdisciplinary projects.	Collaboration logs, peer feedback.	Project Manager, Peer Leaders
C. Non-Education Graduates nor Earners					
Build foundational Data Analysis skills	Achieve basic competency in data analysis by year-end.	Competent basic analysis skills.	Introductory courses and hands-on training sessions.	Regular quizzes, competency-based assessments.	Professional Development Coordinator
Develop basic Assessment Design skills	Design basic assessment tools within nine months.	Effective basic assessment tools.	Step-by-step design tutorials and collaborative projects.	Continuous progress tracking, peer assessments.	Instructional Designer, Peer Support Group

Promote Collaboration	Participate in at least three collaborative projects a year.	Enhanced team-based teaching strategies.	Basic collaboration training and team-building activities.	Collaboration project reviews, team feedback.	Collaboration Coach, Team Leaders
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Conclusion

In conclusion, the study reveals that the length of teaching experience does not significantly affect the assessment literacy of tertiary instructors. This suggests that whether instructors have been teaching for a short time or many years, their assessment skills are similar. However, there is a significant difference in assessment literacy based on educational background, with Education Graduates demonstrating notably higher skills compared to Non-Education Graduates or Earners. Specifically, Education Graduates excel in Collaboration and Assessment Design, areas where they have significantly higher mean scores. These findings underscore the critical role of formal education in equipping instructors with superior assessment skills, particularly in designing assessments. Overall, while tertiary instructors generally demonstrate high assessment literacy, there are clear areas for improvement, particularly in data analysis. This highlights the importance of ongoing professional development to further enhance the quality of teaching and learning in higher educational institutions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, it is recommended that higher educational institutions prioritize professional development programs aimed at enhancing assessment literacy among their instructors. These programs should focus on improving skills in Data Analysis, Assessment Design, and Collaboration, especially for instructors who do not have an education background. Education Graduates, who demonstrate higher assessment literacy, should also be encouraged to participate in advanced workshops and mentorship programs to further strengthen their skills, particularly in data analysis. Institutions should implement a structured monitoring system to track progress and effectiveness, ensuring that these initiatives lead to measurable improvements in teaching quality and student outcomes. By investing in ongoing professional development and support, institutions can effectively cultivate a more skilled and proficient faculty, thereby enhancing the overall educational experience for students.

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